

ADDITIONAL EXPLANATIONS for provided graphs & files

BAM files

BAM files are binary versions of the SAM files, the standard text format for alignment data. These files can be used to examine the distribution of reads, the coverage at each position and the structure of transcripts (see **Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Visualization of reads along TP53 using a BAM file (example)

BAM files may also be used to visualize sequence variants as compared with the reference genome (see **Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Visualization of a sequence variant using a BAM file (example)

Bigwig files

Bigwig files allow the visualization of read depth, i.e. the number of sequenced reads mapping to a given location of the genome. These files are smaller than the BAM files and very convenient to visualize the expression of transcripts and exons in different samples. Of note, the read depth in the bigwig files we provide is normalized against the total number of reads of each sample, so that the height of peaks at a given position may be used to visually compare the expression level between two samples. If the protocol used for library preparation was stranded, two separate bigwig files are provided for forward and reverse reads (see **Figure 3**), allowing to precisely infer the expression of each gene, even when several genes overlap in different directions (e.g. antisense RNAs).

Figure 3: Visualization of gene expression using bigwig files (example)